

Supplementary Information for

Taphonomic megabiases constrain phylogenetic information in the squamate fossil record

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Figure S1. Stage-level occurrences and abundances of major squamate lineages, mapped onto the time-calibrated morphology-based hypothesis of squamate relationships from Gauthier et al. (2012). Gray vertical elongate ovals indicate stage-level range of fossil squamate taxa within a lineage. Dots indicate the occurrence of a species in the geologic stage, and the color of the dot corresponds to that stage. Dark gray horizontal bars indicate the Cretaceous-Paleogene mass extinction event (K-Pg, top) and the End-Triassic Mass Extinction event (ETME, bottom).

Figure S2. Heat map of Epoch-level median Character Completeness Percentage 2 (CCM2) for major squamate lineages, mapped onto the time-calibrated morphology-based hypothesis of squamate relationships from Gauthier et al. (2012). White horizontal bars indicate the Cretaceous-Paleogene mass extinction event (K-PG, top) and the End-Triassic Mass Extinction event (ETME, bottom).

Mann-Whitney U-Test

Lineage	SS differences ($p < \alpha$)?	Which lineage(s)?	SS differences ($0.05 > p > \alpha$)?	Which lineage(s)?
Squamata indet. (SqI)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	ScI; C; An
Scincomorpha indet. (ScI)	<i>Yes</i>	S; Mos	<i>Yes</i>	SqI; G; AI; Am; V; Mon
Anguimorpha indet. (AI)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	I; L; ScI; Pa; C; An; Xa; Xe
Gekkonomorpha (G)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	I; L; ScI; Pa; Sc; An; Xa
†Paramadellodidae (Pa)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	G; Mos; AI; V
Cordylidae (C)	<i>No</i>		<i>Yes</i>	G; Mos; AI; SqI; Am; V; Mon
Scincoidea (Sc)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	G; Mos; AI; Mon
Xantusiidae (Xa)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	G; Mos; AI; Mon
Polyglyphanodontia (Po)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	Mos
Teiioidea (T)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	Mos
Amphisbaenia (Am)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	I; L; ScI; Sc; C; An
Lacertoidea (L)	<i>Yes</i>	S; Mos	<i>Yes</i>	G; AI; Am; V; Mos
†Mosasauria (Mos)	<i>Yes</i>	I; S; L; ScI; An	<i>Yes</i>	Po; T; Pa; Sc; C; Xa; Xe
Serpentes (S)	<i>Yes</i>	G; I; SqI; ScI; AI; Pa; Sc; Xa; Po; T; Am; Mos; L; An; Mon; V	<i>Yes</i>	C
Xenosauria (Xe)	<i>No</i>		<i>Yes</i>	Mos; AI
Anguioidea (An)	<i>Yes</i>	S; Mos	<i>Yes</i>	G; AI; Am; SqI; V; Mon
Monstersauria (Mon)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	L; ScI; Sc; C; An; Xa
Varanoidea (V)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	L; ScI; Pa; C; An
Iguania (I)	<i>Yes</i>	S; Mos	<i>Yes</i>	G; AI; Am

Table S1. Summary of statistical comparisons (Mann-Whitney U-Test) of the median values of CCM2 distributions for major squamate clades. Blue column: results of statistical tests run with a Bonferroni correction on the α -value. Orange column: results depicting p-values of statistical tests between 0.05 and the Bonferroni-corrected α -value.

Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

Lineage	SS differences ($p < \alpha$)?	Which lineage(s)?	SS differences ($0.05 > p > \alpha$)?	Which lineage(s)?
Squamata indet. (SqI)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	I; L; ScI; Pa; Sc; C; A; Xa
Scincomorpha indet. (ScI)	<i>Yes</i>	S; Mos	<i>Yes</i>	SqI; G; AI; Am; V; Mon
Anguimorpha indet. (AI)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	I; L; ScI; Sc; Pa; C; An; Xa; Xe
Gekkonomorpha (G)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	I; L; ScI; Pa; Sc; An; Xa
†Paramadellodidae (Pa)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	G; Mos; SqI; AI; V
Cordylidae (C)	<i>No</i>		<i>Yes</i>	G; Mos; AI; SqI; Am; V; Mon
Scincoidea (Sc)	<i>Yes</i>	S; Mos	<i>Yes</i>	G; AI; SqI; V; Mon
Xantusiidae (Xa)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	G; Mos; AI; V; Mon; SqI
Polyglyphanodontia (Po)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	Mos; L; An
Teiioidea (T)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>No</i>	
Amphisbaenia (Am)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	I; Mos; ScI; Sc; C; An
Lacertoidea (L)	<i>Yes</i>	S; Mos	<i>Yes</i>	G; AI; Po; SqI; V; Mos
†Mosasauria (Mos)	<i>Yes</i>	I; S; L; ScI; Sc; An	<i>Yes</i>	Po; Am; Pa; C; Xa; Xe
Serpentes (S)	<i>Yes</i>	G; I; SqI; ScI; AI; Pa; Sc; Xa; Po; T; Am; Mos; L; An; Mon; V	<i>Yes</i>	C; Xe
Xenosauria (Xe)	<i>No</i>		<i>Yes</i>	S; Mos; AI; V
Anguioidea (An)	<i>Yes</i>	S; Mos	<i>Yes</i>	G; I; Po; AI; Am; SqI; V; Mon
Monstersauria (Mon)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	I; L; ScI; Sc; C; An; Xa
Varanoidea (V)	<i>Yes</i>	S	<i>Yes</i>	I; Xe; L; ScI; Pa; C; An
Iguania (I)	<i>Yes</i>	S; Mos	<i>Yes</i>	G; SqI; AI; Am; An; V; Mon

Table S2. Summary of statistical comparisons (Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test) of the cumulative distributions of CCM2 values for major squamate clades. Blue column: results of statistical tests run with a Bonferroni correction on the α -value. Orange column: results depicting p-values of statistical tests between 0.05 and the Bonferroni-corrected α -value.

Dataset S1 (separate file). Excel spreadsheet of taxon, specimen, and locality information from the Paleobiology Database and from primary literature.

Dataset S2 (separate file). Excel workbook of statistical tests performed in this study.

Dataset S3 (separate file). R Code for analyses carried out in this study

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